

Dimension of religiosity: A psychological viewpoint

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There are cultural disparities in religion, for scholars; evaluating religion is a challenging assignment, because of the multidimensional nature, diversity, and variability of religion and its activities, it offers special contests for the construction of psychometrically sound instruments of the concept. Although measuring religion may necessitate extraordinary research efforts on the part of researchers, it could also be a "boon" for the field's continued creditability, acquiescence as a subject of interest in sociocultural scientific research, and psychology for psychological adjustment and clinical psychology research. While the evaluation of spirituality and religion has advanced significantly over the past few decades, the dominant model of intrinsic and extrinsic religiousness in the psychology of religion—has come under growing scrutiny. Despite Gorsuch's (1984) warning to the contrary, several additional measures have been devised. The path of the sector's new legislation reflects how strongly personal nature has been adopted by religion and spirituality, its postmodern offspring. Additionally, there are still issues with several measurement-related complications, including bias, Social attractiveness, ceiling effects, illusory spiritual health, and lack of definitional accuracy. This article reviews popular international and Indian tools for measuring religion that have good theoretical underpinnings and psychometric qualities.

Keywords: Religion, Religious Fundamentalism, Spirituality, Faith

INTRODUCTION

Religious concerns in people's lives have an impact on multiple areas of scientific psychology, including applied rehabilitative psychology, counseling services, and clinical and health psychology. Spirituality and religion are vital aspects of our culture, and they both affect a person's personality and lifestyle. It is the universal assumption that people believe in a God who lives in the shape of a man (Although this belief is debatable). The terms "religiosity" and "belief in God" are often used interchangeably. Religion represents a group of people who adhere to a belief system, activities, or ideas. As a result, religion is a social practice that focuses on a belief system that includes values, laws and rituals. It is constructed around the social relationship. This is based on Clarke and Jennings's (2008) most recent definition of religion, which is the most relevant to this topic. Religion is generally related to components of thought and conduct, such as spirituality that is rooted in a religious community or tradition and is associated with the

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holiness or supernatural. Religion plays a significant impact in shaping and directing an individual's social and personal life. Zinnbauer et al., (1997), discovered that the study of the original religion would include all aspects of what is now known as spirituality, implying that the separation between spirituality and religion originated as a result of disenchantment with secular ideology and religious organizations. Embers of each religion have similar values and beliefs and as a result, they constitute a kind of societal organization. Religious motives often impact an individual's inner experiences, personal values, and every meaning assigned to life (Park, 2005; Roccas & Elster, 2013). Examined in light of several clinical data, Watts and Williams (1988), aimed to offer a psychological model of religious knowledge. He believes it is a result of the patient's psychotherapy-acquired insight and comprehension. It has been discovered that there is a complex interaction between the mind, body and soul.

Religious views have been reported to influence societal concerns, intergroup relations, and group membership (Goplen & Plant, 2015; Hunsberger & Jackson, 2005). As a consequence, it has a significant impact on a variety of social and psychological concerns. Because the intellectual and dignified people of society remain mute, some anti-social persons create societal discrimination by incorrectly defining religion. This is what? It's referred to as the loss of religion. Politicians are currently chosen based on their religious beliefs since voters from all religions; cast their ballots without merely considering the opinions of their spiritual leaders. Superstition can be seen in this situation. Because adherents of each religion have their unique views, religion is currently the root of conflicts around the globe. It is external and organized.

Tools to Measure Religiosity: International Perspective

1. Religious Fundamentalism Scale – This scale was developed by Altmeyer and Hunsberger in 1992, it consists of 20- items and a five-point rating, a self-report measure of religious fundamentalism. To regulate the impacts of answer sets, ten of the items are phrased in the portrait direction, while the other ten are worded in the contract direction. Internal consistency reliability coefficients for the RFS ranged from .93 to .95.

2. Religiosity and Spirituality Scale for Youth (RaSSY; pilot version) - (Hernandez, 2011) this test was developed by (Hernandez, 2011), A 4-point rating scale with a range of 0 to 3 is used for its 37 items. Never (0), 'Almost often' (3) denote the extent to which respondents engage in or concur with each item. Now scale has two factors- 1. The Faith-based Coping category has 22 entries; they

denote the application of knowledge, religious convictions, and prayer to find courage, comfort, direction, or relief. 2. Labeled religious social support/ activities, it contains 15 statements that highlight participation in various religious pursuits and religious communities. Low and High RaSSY scores indicated low RSL and high RSL respectively. Cronbach's alpha coefficient is used to validate the instrument. According to Hernandez (2011), the survey shows good composite internal consistency ($\alpha=.95$) and strong composite reliability ($r=.85$).

3. Religiosity Scale – This scale was developed by Decker and Broota (1985). It examines a person's loyalty to their religious doctrines and the extent of a person's dependency on the supernatural being. There are 44 items on this scale, out of which 25 were positively framed and 19 were negatively framed. The split-half technique was used to establish the reliability of the scale. By the odd-even method, this scale's items were divided into two identical forms. The half-test reliability coefficient was 0.91. The resulting tenets were 0.96 after being corrected for length using the Spearman-Brown technique. That's why; the religiosity scale's reliability coefficient is 0.96.

4. The Faith Maturity Scale (FMS) - This test was created by Benson, Donahue, & Erickson (1993). It consists of 38 items and is a self-report questionnaire created by the Search Institute for a nationwide study of six mainline Protestant congregations. The FMS is computed based on the 38 items, with a range of 1 to 7. The adult average among the five denominations was 4.63, according to Benson et al., (1993). The reliability coefficients (Cronbach Alpha) varied between .84 and .89. The data supported the development of a four-stage faith maturity typology. Horizontal (low vertical, high horizontal), Undeveloped faith (low vertical, low horizontal), verticals (high vertical, low horizontal), and integrated faith (low vertical, high horizontal) are the four varieties of faith (high vertical, high horizontal). This instrument's 12-item version was constructed using factor analysis and has internal consistency reliability of .88 and a correlation with the long form (Benson et al., a). In conclusion, the FMS is a promising indicator of spiritual growth when compared to national norms. It has good psychometric qualities, but it has not been tested on evangelical or Catholic samples.

5. Religious Maturity Scale:

5. Religious Maturity Scale: This test was created by Cruise and Dudley in 1990. After a detailed examination of Allport's (1950) argument, a fully developed religion should be "highly differentiated; dynamic in character despite its derived origin; productive of a

consistent morality; comprehensive; integral; and fundamentally heuristic," they developed the RMS (Dudely & Cruise, p.98, citing Allport). Additionally, they utilize a psychological framework rather than a theological one to determine religious maturity. 'When a new aspect of the 'truth' becomes clear to me, I want to be prepared to advance in my understanding. 'The religious maturity individual believes, according to this scale. Meanwhile, I'll make to with the light I have.'"(p. 101 in Cruise & Dudley), There are 11 items on the scale. Three items with low scores measure the immaturity of religion, whereas eight positively scored items assess religious maturity. Catholic and Seventh-day Adventist university students who used the RMS were reviewed by older teenagers and small-group adults who attended various religious events. For internal consistency, the reported value of the coefficient alpha was 0.55, showing that the items are diverse. Cruise and Dudley discovered that their scale had a 0.37 correlation with the Quest in terms of validity.

6. Personal Religiosity Inventory: Lips Meyer (1984) constructed a multidimensional religiosity scale; PRI consists of 45 items and nine subscales. The scale assesses ritual attendance (RA), personal prayer (PRP), belief in God (BLFGOD), non-ritual, church-related activity (NRA), belief in an afterlife (AFTERLIFE), the subjective experience of drawing near to God (CLOSEGOD), the perceived alignment of religious beliefs with attitude on moral and social issues (RSM), the level to which a person's beliefs about religion shape their philosophy or way of life (IDEO), and integration (the degree to which a person (INT). While some of the questions are multiple-choice or yes/no, almost all of them use a 6-point Likert scale. For this study, multiple-choice items were broken down into separate questions. Consequently, the PRI used in this investigation has 77 statements. For the nine scales in the adult population, 0.83 to 0.97 was reported as the test-retest reliability coefficient for the PRI over seven days. Lipsmeyer found that the PRI showed great concurrent validity, with religious experts (nuns, priests) scoring much upper than the general population on all scales. The scores of atheists, agnostics, and nonreligious people were significantly lower than those of other major religious groups (Lipsmeyer).

7. The Personal Religiosity Scale (PRS)- It was developed in Taiwan by Soong and Li (1988). The PRS is made up of 37 components and is divided into eight factors. The factors' names and definitions are as given: (a) Religious belief- holds a firm religious belief; (b) Nature/ Environmental factors, like as fengshui, may influence an individual's well-being and wealth; (c) Good vs. Evil-

God will reward the good while punishing the bad. (e) Value/happiness of life- experiences values and happiness in life, (f) Afterlife- believes in afterlife and reincarnation, (g) Physical substance quality/Chinese medicine beliefs- believes that various physical substances have varied qualities that influence health, and pregnancy is overseen by a god. For each item in the original PRS, a 4-point Likert scale is used.

Tools to measure religiosity: Indian Perspective

1. Religiosity Test: known as the religiosity scale was originally developed by L.I. Bhushan and adopted by Jayaprakash with some modifications keeping in view the nature of research work and sample. This scale consists of 36 items and 5 point liker type scale. The possible score range of this scale is 36 – 180. The higher the score on the religiosity scale, the higher the degree of religiosity. The temporal stability coefficient of this scale was determined by the method of test- retest.. Test-retest reliability is 0.517. Similarly, the internal consistency reliability of the scale was calculated by product-moment correlation and determined by the Superman Brown prophecy formula. The reliability coefficient is given below. A Split-half 0.57 Spearman-Brown Prophecy 0.72

L.I. Bhushan's religiosity scale was used to validate the religiosity scale. ($r=0.69$) was calculated as the product-moment correlation.

2. Indic Religiosity scale: (Tulsi Jayakumar & Anshul Verma, 2020) The creation of a 15-item construct with five components that serves as a valid and reliable test of religiosity with five components are as follows- A. Way of life, B. Belief in Rebirth, Karma and Destiny, C. Existence of Supreme Power, D. Importance of Prayer, E. Purposeful Life

3. Attitude scale towards religion: This scale was constructed in 1978 by R.K. Ojha. It is a Likert-type scale consisting of 50 statements, which are answered on a five-point scale, the range of possible scores on it is 50-250. The higher the score on this scale, the higher the degree of religiosity.

4. The Centrality of Religiosity Scale (CRS) is a test of the centrality, prominence, or significance of religious connotations in a person's psyche. Huber was the one who came up with the idea. It is made up of 15 items and a five-point rating scale that assesses the general intensity of five fundamental elements of religion as stated by theory. Religious life as a whole is represented by the aspect of religious experience, private practice, public practice, ideology and intellectual component. Five fundamental elements might be seen as psychologically shaping and activating personal religious constructs

as conduits or mechanisms. It is possible to use a person's religious beliefs to determine an individual's centrality from the five-dimensional measures, which apply to interreligious studies as well. The CRS-5 has an internal consistency of 0.85 in the Religion Monitor's Entire sample, 0.93 in the CRS-10, and 0.84 in the CRSi-7 (Crobach's Alphas).

5. Religiosity Questionnaire: Gupta developed the Religiosity Questionnaire (1980). The questionnaire had 50 questions on the four dimensions listed below- 1. Faith in God, 2. Faith in Hell/ Heaven, 3 Faith in religion, 4 Faith in rituals

There are both positive and negative items on the questionnaire. Each item's response was recorded in three columns: Agree, Doubtful, and Disagree. The scoring method used was to score the negative and positive dimensions of the items separately. Agree, Doubtful and Disagree each received a weighting of 2, 1, 0 for the positive items. Agree, Doubtful and Disagree categories were assigned a reverse score of 0, 1, and 2 for negative items. The test's reliability was determined using the test-retest approach, and it was found to be .65 significant at .01 levels. The dependability of the split-half was calculated using the spearman-brown formula and found to be .84. The test's validity was also verified. External criteria of 44 significance at a .05 level were used to estimate convergent validity.

Conclusion: A review of the literature shows that religious thought affects a person's personal life, societal life, inter-group relation and group membership. There is also a lot of cultural disparity in religion. Due to religion and its activities' multiple perspectives, complexity, and heterogeneity, measuring religion is a complex assignment for scholars, which provides unique difficulties for the development of concept-based psychometrically sound instruments. Here various types of national and International tests have been included in this review paper, which will be very beneficial for researchers.

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